

ISic0699

Dedication by an Augustalis

Language

Latin

Type

dedication

Material

marble

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

2017.03.25

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Centuripae

Place of origin (modern)

Centuripe

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Centuripe, Museo Archeologico Regionale di Centuripe

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [Larib(us)A]ugus[tis]
2. [sac]rum
3. L(ucius) Calp[urni]us Aphonetus
4. IIII vir Augustalis

Apparatus

Text after Manganaro 1989

[Genio A]ugus[ti], Libertini

Translation (en)

Sacred to the Lares of Augustus. Lucius Calpurnius Aphonetus, IIIIvir Augustalis (dedicated it)

Commentary

R. Duthoy, 'Les Augustales' in ANRW 2.16.2 (1978), p.1266 notes the oddity of IIII vir Augustalis rather than VIvir. Manganaro suggests an Augustan date, but this is not certain.

Digital identifiers:

TM 175758

EDR 081501

EDCS 13700403

Bibliography

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-17): ISic0699. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4338175>

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